

Interview Questions

Evaluation Process

I'll present constructs from each dimension for your evaluation. For each construct, I'll ask to the participant provide:

- Relevance Rating (1–5 scale): How important is this factor in shaping blockchain developer experience?
- Clarity Assessment (Clear/Not Clear): Is the definition clear and understandable?
- Brief Comments: Any observations or suggestions.

Construct Assessment

For each construct, present:

Construct Name: *e.g., RPC Infrastructure Quality*

Definition: *Brief operational definition*

Dimension: *Dimension A/B/C*

Basic Assessment:

- Relevance: *1=Not Relevant to 5=Highly Relevant*
- Clarity: *Clear/Not Clear*
- Comments: *Open*

Deep Dive Questions (for selected high/low rated or unclear constructs):

If rated 4–5 (HIGH relevance) - Fidelity Validation:

- "Can you share a concrete example of how [CONSTRUCT] affected your work?"
- "Does our definition align with how you experience this in practice?"

If rated 1–2 (LOW relevance):

- "Why do you consider this less relevant to your experience?"

If marked 'Not Clear':

- "What about the definition was unclear?"
- "How would you rephrase it based on your experience?"

Completeness Check (After each dimension)

After completing all constructs in a dimension:

"We've reviewed [N] constructs in [Dimension A/B/C]. Based on your experience:

- Are there any critical factors missing that influence your developer experience in this dimension?

- What other aspects come to mind when you think about this area of developer experience?"

Document emergent constructs

Repeat **Construct Assessment** and **Completeness Check** for each dimension

Applicability Assessment

Practical Scenario

Example: "Imagine you need to choose a BaaS platform for a new project. You receive a BcDEx comparative report showing three platforms with different profiles:

- Platform A: Strong in technical aspects (documentation, infrastructure) but moderate in developer satisfaction.
- Platform B: Strong in satisfaction and community aspects but weaker in some technical areas.
- Platform C: Balanced moderate scores across all aspects."

Questions:

- Would this type of comparative analysis be useful in your decision-making? Why or why not?
- How would you use this information in practice?
- What would make this framework more useful for your real-world needs?

This scenario will be refined as the framework develops.

Feasibility and Actionability

- Could you (or your organization) collect the data needed for this type of assessment? What barriers might exist?
- Does the framework provide actionable insights, or is it too abstract? Can you give an example?

Closing

- How would you evaluate the BcDEx Framework overall?
- Is there anything important we haven't discussed that you'd like to add?